

CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR IN SITI FATIMAH MATERNAL AND CHILD REGIONAL HOSPITAL MAKASSAR

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Abstract

Several factors can influence consumer behaviour when choosing a hospital, particularly for pregnant people, who are healthy individuals with time to consider alternatives and make decisions. According to All Indonesian Hospital Association, the number of hospitals in South Sulawesi has increased by 3.7% in 2020. Therefore, hospitals must attract and retain customers. This study aims to analyse the influence of social factors, cultural factors, economic factors, experiential marketing, patient satisfaction, and service innovation on repurchase intention at Siti Fatimah Maternal and Child Regional Hospital. This is an observational, cross-sectional study. The sample in this study was outpatient and inpatient obstetric patients with repeat visits (n = 90), selected proportionally. Data in this study were analysed using the Spearman correlation test using the SPSS version 26.0. This research shows that economic factor ($p < 0.000$, $\rho = -0.386$), experiential marketing ($p = 0.041$, $\rho = 0.216$), and patient satisfaction ($p = 0.011$, $\rho = 0.268$) influences repurchase intention. While experiential marketing ($p < 0.000$, $\rho = 0.646$) and service innovation ($p = 0.011$, $\rho = 0.268$) have an impact on patient satisfaction. It is concluded that the factors influencing repurchase intention are economic factors, experiential marketing and patient satisfaction. Patient satisfaction is influenced by experiential marketing and service innovation.

Keywords: Social Factors, Cultural Factors, Economic Factors, Consumer Behaviour, Experiential Marketing.

INTRODUCTION

Hospital is a health care institution that organises comprehensive individual health services that provide inpatient, outpatient and emergency services [1]. Meanwhile, the number of hospitals in South Sulawesi increased by 3.7% in 2020, with the most specialised hospitals being mother and child hospitals, with 25 hospitals [2]. This shows that the growth rate of hospitals is increasing, thus increasing competition in the hospital industry in Indonesia. This condition triggers hospitals in Indonesia to be able to do customer retention.

Loyalty is the intention to return to the same service provider or to recommend the service provider to others [3]. Repurchase intention is one of the sub-dimensions of customer loyalty, i.e. a customer's personal desire to maintain a relationship with a service provider and to use services repeatedly from the same provider [4].

High levels of customer satisfaction lead to better customer loyalty, which in turn leads to better business performance. Customer satisfaction depends on the perceived value compared to the buyer's expectations [5]. Favourable customer perceptions of quality are positively related to overall customer satisfaction and patient behaviour intentions; repurchase intentions and intention to recommend quality to others [6].

There are several demographic factors that influence consumer behaviour, namely age, gender, marital status, income, family background, education level, occupation, family size, geographical factors and psychological factors [7]. External influences

(culture, subculture, reference group, social class, family, roles and status) as well as internal influences (personality, perception, motivation, learning, beliefs, attitude, lifestyle, profession, education, age, and income) influence the consumer buyer behaviour [8].

People who have a normal pregnancy are healthy people who have the time to gather information, consider the alternatives and make an informed decision. Pregnant people make their own choices of hospitals. They are strongly influenced by personal or peer experiences. Furthermore, this decision-making process makes pregnant people very sensitive to differences between preferred hospitals [9].

In the digital era, innovation in an organisation aims to achieve customer satisfaction and loyalty, and ensure survival and success rates. Companies are using service innovation to gain competitive advantage in this dynamic environment [10]. With the changing paradigm of hospitals entering the free market, regulatory developments, increasing public demand for healthcare services, and technological developments in healthcare, hospitals need to innovate [11].

Experiential marketing has a strong influence on patient behaviour, which can create satisfaction and loyalty to the hospital [12]. Experiential marketing helps to create a better brand image, increase customer loyalty and retention, and even attract new customers [13].

Siti Fatimah Regional Specialised Hospital for Mothers and Children is one of the specialised hospitals under the South Sulawesi Provincial Government in cooperation with the Social Security Organisation (SSO). RSKDIA Siti Fatimah introduces service innovations such as free ultrasound examination. From the first half of 2021 to the second half of 2022, the growth of non-SSO patients with repeat visits at RSKDIA Siti Fatimah has decreased by 63%. Patients who do not use the SSO can go directly to any type of hospital and any location of their choice [14]. Therefore, this study aims to find out the consumer behaviour factors at RSKDIA Siti Fatimah and the factors that can influence the repurchase intention.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Methodology of the Study and Subjects

This was a quantitative study conducted at the Siti Fatimah Maternal and Child Regional Hospital in Makassar City using an analytical observational approach with a cross-sectional design. The study sample included obstetric patients with repeat visits from inpatient and outpatient department, both with and without SSO. A total of 90 respondents were surveyed during the data collection period from 26 June 2023 to 21 July 2023. Proportional random sampling was applied by calculating the ratio of inpatients to outpatients in 2021-2022 to obtain the proportion of samples from inpatient and outpatient facilities.

Calculation of the Sample Size

Researchers conducted preliminary research to determine the proportion of patients with repurchase intention on 15 May 2023 at 08.00-10.00 involving 16 respondents, consisting of 11 inpatients and 5 outpatients. The ratio is taken from the comparison of obstetric patients with repeat visits in the outpatient and inpatient departments during 2021-2022. The results of the proportions were obtained as follows.

$$p = \frac{10}{16} = 0.625$$

The sample size was determined using the Lemeshow formula,

$$n = \frac{N \cdot Z^2_{1-\alpha/2} \cdot p \cdot q}{d^2(N-1) + Z^2_{1-\alpha/2} \cdot p \cdot q} = \frac{6004 \cdot 1.96^2 \cdot 0.625 \cdot 0.375}{0.1^2(6004-1) + 1.96^2 \cdot 0.625 \cdot 0.375} = 88.72 \approx 89$$

This study used an estimated proportion of 0.625 from the preliminary study, an absolute precision of 10%, an α value of 5%, and a Z value of 1.96. The population size was taken from the total number of obstetric patients with a history of repeat visits in 2021-2022.

A sample size of about 89 people would be appropriate to achieve the required level of confidence and margin of error, taking into account the possibility of incomplete questionnaires. This would be determined by rounding the total population up to the nearest whole number.

The questionnaire was in Bahasa Indonesia and the researcher communicated with the respondents through direct question and answer. All participants were fully aware of their participation in this study and it was voluntary, and confidentiality was maintained at all times.

Survey or Questionnaire

The questionnaire used was in Indonesian and consisted of seven sections, namely:

Respondent Demographic

This section of the survey asked seven questions about the respondent's demographic information, including age, ethnicity, religion, education level, occupation and income level. Questions on income level were used in the calculation of economic factors, measured by income level categories from the Central Bureau of Statistics.

Screening Question

This section asked whether the patient visited the hospital on her own intention and whether the patient has visited the hospital several times.

Social Factors

Social factors are measured using a three-question questionnaire used in previous research with dimensions of this variable include friends, family, and social roles and status [15].

Cultural Factors

Cultural factors were measured using a three-question questionnaire from previous research with dimensions of this variable are people's habits, geographic area, and ethnicity [15].

Economic Factors

Economic factors were measured using a one-question questionnaire on respondent characteristics with income level categories from the Central Bureau of Statistics.

Experiential Marketing

The questionnaire regarding experiential marketing is measured using five indicators, namely sense, feel, think, act, and relate. The questionnaire used consists of 21 questions taken from previous research [16].

Service Innovation

A questionnaire with six questions regarding service innovation developed from previous research dimensions, namely innovative services, development of new processes or systems, and strategic innovations that are attractive to customers [17].

Patient Satisfaction

Patient satisfaction was measured on the basis of the Patient Satisfaction Questionnaire - 18 with 18 questions and acceptable reliability test results [18].

Repurchase Intention

The repurchase intention questionnaire consists of six questions and is based on a questionnaire developed from the dimensions of previous research, namely considering this hospital when making a return visit, always visiting this hospital even though other hospitals are said to be better, and will always visit this hospital [19].

This instrument has been tested for construct validity and reliability using 30 respondents at Pertiwi Maternal and Child Regional Hospital, Makassar. The reliability test results show that all question items in this research questionnaire are reliable, as seen from the Cronbach's alpha value of > 0.60 . The results of the validity test showed that there were five invalid questions, which were excluded from the research phase, as seen from the person correlation value $> r$ table (0.3061), which ranges from -0.199 to 0.909.

Analysis of the Data

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.00 was used during the data analysis process. The data were first processed to determine the univariate breakdown of the demographic percentages. The Kormogorov-Smirnov test was carried out to test the normality of the data and, as the data were not normally distributed, the Spearman correlation test was carried out to see if there was a significant influence of repurchase intention on the various social, cultural and economic factors, experiential marketing, service innovation and patient satisfaction included in the sample.

Ethical Considerations

This study received ethical approval from the Health Research Ethics Commission, Faculty of Public Health, Universitas Hasanuddin on 09 June 2023, number: 3961/UN4.14.1/TP.01.02/2023.

RESULTS

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Respondents' Characteristics and the Crosstabulation with Repurchase Intention (n=90)

Variables	Repurchase Intention*				Total	
	Yes		No		n	%
	n	%	n	%		
Age (Years)						
< 20	10	91%	1	9%	11	12.2%
20-35	54	76%	17	24%	71	78.9%
>35	5	63%	3	38%	8	8.9%
Occupation						
Students	1	100%	0	0%	1	1.1%
Self-employed	2	67%	1	33%	3	3.3%
Private employee	3	38%	5	63%	8	8.9%
Housewife	64	82%	14	18%	78	86.7%
Education Level						
Elementary school	12	92%	1	8%	13	14.4%
Junior high school	16	84%	3	16%	19	21.1%
Senior high school	34	77%	10	23%	44	48.9%
Diploma	1	100%	0	0%	1	1.1%
Graduate	7	54%	6	46%	13	14.4%
Ethnicity						
Makassar	44	81%	10	19%	54	60%
Bugis	19	68%	9	32%	28	31.1%
Others*	6	75%	2	25%	8	8.9%
Religion						
Moslem	68	78%	19	22%	87	96.7%
Catholic	1	33%	2	67%	3	3.3%
Income Level (Rp)						
<1.500.000	63	80%	16	20%	79	87.8%
1500000-2500000	4	80%	1	20%	5	5.6%
2500000-3500000	1	50%	1	50%	2	2.2%
>3.500.000	1	25%	3	75%	4	4.4%

*Others are Torajanese (2 respondents), Mandarese (1 respondents), Manggarai (1 respondents), Javanese (1 respondents), Muna (1 respondents), Tolakinese (1 respondents), and Poso (1 respondents). Source: Primary Data, 2023

The characteristics of the respondents who visited the hospital are shown in Table 1. The majority of respondents were between 20 and 35 years old, 71 respondents (78.9%), and the majority of respondents were housewives, 78 respondents (86.7%). The highest level of education was senior high school with 44 respondents (48.9%). The most common ethnicity was Makassar with 54 respondents (60%) and religion was Islam with 87 respondents (96.7%). Finally, the highest income level was < Rp.1,500,000 with 79 respondents (87.8%).

In addition, table 1 also shows a cross tabulation of the characteristics of respondents on Repurchase Intention. The Yes / No group on Repurchase Intention is determined based on the median of the data, namely 24. In the age category, the highest repurchase rate is in the <20 years age category, namely 10 people (91%), while the lowest repurchase rate is in the >35 years age group, namely 5 people (63%). In the employment category, the highest repurchase rate is in the student category, namely 1 person (100%), while the lowest repurchase rate is in the private employee group, namely 3 people (38%). In the education level category, the highest repurchase rate

is in the Diploma category, namely 1 person (100%), while the lowest repurchase rate is in the Bachelor group, namely 7 people (54%). In the ethnic category, the highest repurchase rate is in the Makassar ethnic category, namely 44 people (81%), while the lowest repurchase rate is in the Bugis ethnic group, namely 19 people (68%). In the religion category, the highest repurchase rate is in the Islamic religion group, namely 68 people (78%), while the lowest repurchase rate is in the Catholic religion group, namely 1 person (33%). In the category of monthly income level, the highest repurchase rate is in the category of income below Rp. 1,500,000.00, namely 63 people (80%), while the lowest repurchase rate is in the Catholic religion group, namely 1 person (33%). In the monthly income level category, the highest repurchase rate is in the income category below Rp. 1,500,000.00, namely 63 people (80%), while the lowest repurchase rate is in the income group above Rp. 3,500,000.00, namely 1 person (25%).

The results of this cross-tabulation in Table 1 also show that there is a downward trend in the expression of repurchase intentions with each increase in monthly income level.

Table 2: Distribution of Social Factors, Cultural Factors, Experiential Marketing, Service Innovation, Patient Satisfaction, and Repurchase Intention (n=90)

Variables	Mean	SD	Median	High		Low	
				n	%	n	%
Social Factors	19.39	3.71	20	49	54.4%	41	45.6%
Cultural Factors	20.74	4.39	21	47	52.2%	43	47.8%
Experiential Marketing	78.86	5.37	78	57	63.3%	33	36.7%
Service Innovation	20.96	3.55	21	46	51.1%	44	48.9%
Patient Satisfaction	72.69	2.95	72	75	83.3%	15	16.7%
Repurchase Intention	25.41	3.470	24	69	76.7%	21	23.3%

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Notes: High/Yes and Low/No are categorised based on the median of the data because the data are not normally distributed.

Social factors, cultural factors, experiential marketing, service innovation, patient satisfaction, and repurchase intention are all numerical data. Data are therefore statistically presented as mean, SD and median in Table 2 and median was taken as the midline dividing the high and low categories, as the data were not normally distributed (Table 3).

Table 3: Normality of Data (n=90)

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	p-value
Social Factors	Repurchase intention	0,000
Cultural Factors		0,000
Economic Factors		0,000
Experiential marketing		0,011
Service innovation		0,000
Patient satisfaction		0,001
Experiential marketing	Patient Satisfaction	0,000
Service innovation		0,000

The highest percentage of respondents in the high category is patient satisfaction with 75 respondents (83.3%), followed by repurchase intention with 69 respondents (76.7%), experiential marketing with 57 respondents (63.3%), cultural factors with 49

respondents (54.4%), cultural factors with 47 respondents (52.2%), and the lowest is service innovation with 46 respondents (51.1%).

It can be concluded that the data in this study are not normally distributed when looking at the data in Table 3 (p-value <0.05). For this reason, the influence between the variables was tested using the Spearman correlation test.

Table 4: Correlation between Independent and Dependent Variables

Independent Variables	Dependent Variables	ρ	p-value
Social Factors	Repurchase intention	-0,005	0,962
Cultural Factors		-0,052	0,627
Economic Factors		-0.386	0.000*
Experiential marketing		0,216	0,041*
Service innovation		0,167	0,116
Patient satisfaction		0,268	0,011*
Experiential marketing	Patient Satisfaction	0,646	0,000*
Service innovation		0,297	0,004*

The Spearman correlation test results are shown in Table 4. Variables that have a correlation on repurchase intention are economic factors (p=0.000), experiential marketing (p=0.041) and patient satisfaction (p=0.011). On the other hand, experiential marketing (p=0.000) and service innovation (p=0.004) have a correlation on patient satisfaction. On the other hand, no correlation on repurchase intention was found for social factors (p=0.962), cultural factors (p=0.627) and service innovation (p=0.116).

DISCUSSION

Consumer Behaviour is the study of individuals, groups or organisations and the process of selecting and using goods or services to meet needs, and the impact of this selection process on consumers and society, as well as the mental and social processes that accompany these actions [20]. Different factors and characteristics influence the individual consumer's decision making process, shopping habits, purchasing behaviour, the brands they buy or the retailers they visit, resulting in purchase decisions [21]. Social factors such as small consumer groups, social networks, family and social roles and status also influence consumer behaviour [5].

It is important to explore the influence of social factors on repurchase intention because most of the factors that influence consumer behaviour are beyond the control of marketers. Marketers need to understand the complexities of consumer behaviour and seek information about their customers to identify their needs and behaviours [20].

Based on the results of the research conducted at Siti Fatimah Maternal and Child Regional Hospital Makassar, there is no significant influence between social factors on repurchase intention (p=0.962). Reference groups are not an important factor for more than half of respondents. However, 55.5% of respondents said that family approval was an important factor in purchasing needs and services [22]. There is no significant relationship between social factors (influence of family and reference groups) and the decision to buy, but rather personal and cultural factors [23];[24]; [25].

However, other studies have shown that social factors have a significant impact on the decision to buy and on customer loyalty [26]; [27]. This also contradicts consumer behaviour theory, which suggests that social factors influence repurchase intention. In addition, there are other factors that can influence consumer behaviour, namely

internal factors, which consist of motivation, perception, learning, beliefs and attitudes [21]. The presence of other factors may influence the repurchase intention of the respondents at Siti Fatimah Hospital, which have not been investigated in this study.

A p-value of 0.627 was then found for the cultural factors examined with the dimensions of community habits, geographical area and ethnicity using the Spearman correlation test. This shows that cultural factors do not significantly influence repurchase intention. Similar to the results of the above study, there is no positive influence of cultural factors, patient characteristics (education, employment, economic conditions and payment methods, family social factors) on patients' choices of hospitalisation. Instead, social characteristics of reference groups and psychological factors [28]. The study also looked at reference groups. However, no effect on repurchase intention was found. This may be because 54% of respondents are Makassarese, which is the majority ethnicity in Makassar City [29]. Ethnicity is taken into account when minorities need health services. This is because they think about whether they will be accepted or rejected by the majority [30].

As with social factors, the results of this study contradict consumer behaviour theory. This suggests that the similarities between these two variables are due to other unexamined factors in the consumer environment.

Economic models emphasise using the least cost to achieve the greatest benefit, which emphasises consumer spending patterns. Therefore, consumer spending behaviour can be predicted using economic indicators such as consumer purchasing power and competitive product prices [31]. There is a weak negative correlation between economic factors assessed by income level on repurchase intention ($p=0.000$, $\rho=-0.386$). Age, gender, marital status, income, family background, education level, occupation, family size, geographical factors and psychological factors are some of the demographic factors that influence consumer behaviour [7]; [32]. Social, cultural, economic, personal, and psychological factors influence purchases [33]. The main reasons for using health services in government health facilities were affordability (67%) and convenient location (60%) [34]. Revisit intentions vary by income category and price perception decreases with income level [35]. As incomes rise, so do patients' expectations and knowledge of medical services [36]. Contrary to the results obtained, the financing factor has a positive effect on purchase intention [37]. There are also studies that show that the financial motivation does not have a significant effect on the intention to visit a tourist attraction [38].

There is a weak positive correlation between experiential marketing on repurchase intention ($p=0.041$, $\rho=0.216$). Experiential marketing positively and significantly affects repurchase intention [39]; [40]; [41]; [42]. Experiential marketing can significantly influence revisit intention [43]. Consistent with this research, experiential marketing has a positive correlation with revisit intention and recommendation [44]. There are also a number of research findings which indicate that experiential marketing does not have a significant impact on the intention to repurchase [45]; [46].

Service innovation was found to have no significant effect on repurchase intention based on the results of the study ($p=0.116$). This finding is in line with research that has found that service innovation does not have a significant effect on repurchase intention, but does have an effect on customer experience, information quality and trust [47]. A positive but insignificant relationship was found between perceived innovativeness and repurchase intention. Variables that have a significant effect are

perceived popularity and patient satisfaction. These are not examined in this study [48].

Experiential marketing has a strong positive correlation on patient satisfaction ($p=0.000$, $\rho=0.646$). These findings are similar to research in the cosmetics industry, which found that experiential marketing had a positive impact on patient satisfaction [13]; [46]; [49]. In a hospital study, experiential marketing significantly impacts on patient satisfaction [50].

There is a weak positive correlation between service innovation and patient satisfaction ($p=0.004$, $\rho=0.297$). This is in line with other research showing that service innovation has a significant impact on patient satisfaction [51]; [52]; [53]; [54]. Service innovation has a positive effect on customer satisfaction in a study conducted in a factory environment [49].

There is a weak positive correlation between service innovation and patient satisfaction ($p=0.011$, $\rho=0.268$). The results of this study are similar to several studies that have found a positive and significant relationship between patient satisfaction and repurchase intention [46]; [55]; [56]; [57]; [58]. Additionally, research shows that repurchase intention can be predicted 53.4% by patient satisfaction [59]. Service quality and patient satisfaction significantly influence intention to return [60].

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this study aims to determine how consumer behaviour factors and factors that can influence repurchase intention at RSKDIA Siti Fatimah. In addition, factors that affect patient satisfaction were also investigated. The paradigm of marketing management science is strongly emphasised as a result of this research, because to improve hospital performance is not only from service quality but also studying factors that only exist in consumers and consumer experience. The study looked at pregnant people who were healthy. This is because healthy people have more things to consider before choosing a hospital. This research emphasises that each individual is different and has their own characteristics. However, it is important to understand that economic factors have a major influence on individual decision making. Market research is important in the study of the characteristics of patients who visit the hospital in order to understand their wants and needs. The focus on patient experience and patient satisfaction should also be a priority. To increase patient satisfaction and encourage patients to return to hospital when they need health services again, the patient experience can be enriched with good service, friendly and courteous staff, complete and comfortable facilities at affordable prices. Future research is expected to expand the scope and types of hospitals studied and to add to the consumer behavior variables evaluated in order to better understand the phenomena occurring in hospital marketing and consumer behavior.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

There are a number of limitations to this study. These include the limited number and type of hospitals surveyed and the use of qualitative questionnaires, which can be influenced by respondents' perceptions.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest

Authorship Contributions

The authors participated in generating the idea, designing the project, collecting and interpreting the data, analysing the results and drafting the manuscript of this research paper.

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